

FINTECH AS A FACTOR OF ASYMMETRIC TRANSFORMATION OF THE BANKING SECTOR: EUROPEAN EXPERIENCE AND POTENTIAL FOR UKRAINE

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ABSTRACT

In the current conditions of digital transformation of the financial sector, FinTech is one of the key drivers of structural changes in banking. The COVID-19 pandemic, the full-scale war in Ukraine, and global digitalization processes have significantly accelerated the introduction of contactless payment technologies, mobile banking, and remote financial services. Special scientific attention is required to analyze the impact of FinTech on the banking systems of developing countries, which simultaneously strive to catch up with digital leaders and face institutional, economic, and infrastructural constraints. Ukraine, being in conditions of military instability, demonstrates unexpectedly high rates of digitalization of banking services, which actualizes the need for its scientific understanding in a comparative international context. The purpose of the study is to analyze the main trends in the development of financial technologies in the banking sector of different countries, in particular, to compare digital transformation in developed and developing countries, to identify success factors, development barriers, and the potential for integrating innovations into the banking sector. The study uses quantitative and comparative approaches. Statistical indicators characterizing access to financial services and the level of digitalization of banking activities are analyzed, in particular, the number of bank branches and ATMs, the volume of mobile and Internet banking transactions, the number of transactions per capita and the share of digital payments in GDP using the example of 11 European countries. Methods of comparative analysis, data visualization and interpretation of digital trends in dynamics are used. The results of the study indicate the presence of pronounced unevenness and asymmetry of the digital transformation of the banking sector under the influence of FinTech. In developed countries (Estonia, Poland, Turkey), FinTech is actually transforming into the dominant banking service channel, which is accompanied by a reduction in physical banking infrastructure, a rapid increase in the number of digital transactions and a high share of non-cash payments in GDP. In contrast, in developing countries (Albania, Kosovo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Moldova), digital financial services are at the stage of formation and are developing in parallel with the physical banking infrastructure, which indicates the catching-up nature of digitalization and limited substitutability of traditional service channels. For Ukraine, despite the lack of complete statistical data in the sample, a specific model of forced digital transformation is characteristic, in which the reduction of physical banking infrastructure is combined with the intensive growth of remote banking services, in particular mobile banking and non-cash payments. This allows to attribute Ukraine to the group of countries with a high potential for accelerated FinTech integration, provided that the institutional and regulatory environment is stabilized. The value of the study lies in identifying and systematizing models of asymmetric FinTech transformation of the banking sector in European countries with different levels of economic development, which allows to explain the absence of a universal trajectory of digitalization. The practical significance of the results obtained lies in the possibility of using them to form strategies for the digital transformation of the banking sector, develop financial inclusion policies, and adapt best European FinTech practices for countries in catching up, in particular for Ukraine.

Keywords: *ICT Sector; FinTech; banking sector; digital transformation; developing countries; IMF Financial Access Survey; digital transactions; cashless payments; banking services market; national economy; Ukraine; Europe.*

1. INTRODUCTION

FinTech have become a powerful driver of transformation of the banking sector. Digitalization covers almost all aspects of banking activities - from opening an account to making transactions, lending, managing savings, identifying customers, etc. Particularly noticeable is growing popularity of mobile and online banking, the number of transactions in which is showing explosive growth in most countries, regardless of the development level of the financial system. This process is not uniform: while Estonia is experiencing a stable and rapid growth of digital services, in developing countries or countries that are only in the transformation stage, FinTech is developing at a slower pace, often facing barriers in the form of weak infrastructure, insufficient digital literacy or imperfect regulation.

Despite the general trend towards digitalization of financial services, there is no clear understanding of how the development of FinTech correlates with changes in traditional banking infrastructure – the number of banks, branches and ATMs – and how these processes affect the availability of financial services in countries at different stages of transformation. The issue of comparability and interpretation of digital activity indicators (the number and value of mobile and Internet banking transactions, their share in GDP, transactional activity per capita) in combination with indicators of the physical presence of banks remains particularly problematic. In countries with catching up development, the lack of comprehensive and comparable data makes it difficult to assess the real level of FinTech penetration and the formation of effective strategies for the digital transformation of the banking sector. This problem is given additional relevance by the situation in Ukraine, where structural changes in the banking system are taking place under the influence of crisis factors, which requires scientific understanding without prior generalizations about the effectiveness of digitalization. This necessitates a systematic comparative analysis of the development of FinTech in the banking sector of different countries in order to identify general patterns, limitations, and potential directions for further development.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, FinTech has become a key factor in transformation of the banking sector in both

developed and developing countries (Aldaarmi [2]; Shkolnyk [42]; Shkarlet et al. [39]; Dubyna et al. [9]). FinTech encompasses a wide range of digital solutions: from mobile payments and online lending to blockchain and artificial intelligence in financial services (Shaposhnykov et al. [36]; Savchenko et al. [34]; Zagirniak et al. [51]).

Studies by Abramova et al. [1], Gancarczyk et al. [12]. and Alieksieiev et al. [3] define FinTech as an evolutionary response to the need for faster, cheaper and more accessible financial services. The authors emphasize that FinTech not only changes service consumption patterns, but also forces banks to adapt, automate processes and innovate. Khudolei et al. [22] and Hidayat-ur-Rehman [15] show that FinTech can reduce transaction costs, increasing the efficiency of financial systems.

In EU countries, the FinTech sector is showing rapid development. According to studies by Zybareva et al. [54], Ivashchenko et al. [20], Li [27] and Kychko et al. [25] regulatory support (e.g., PSD2 in the EU) has contributed to development of open banking and competition in the market. The British FCA has become an example of regulatory sandboxes, which have stimulated innovation.

At the same time, the available scientific literature notes uneven development: southern and eastern EU countries lag behind in the FinTech implementation due to weaker digital infrastructure, lower investment, and caution of banking institutions (Kozmenko et al. [24]; Serdarušić et al. [35]). Bukhtiarova et al. [8]; Hrubliak et al. [16]) identify three main strategies of banks in response to FinTech: cooperation (partnership with FinTech startups), competition (creation of their own digital solutions), and consolidation (acquisitions).

In Ukraine, FinTech is in active formation stage. According to the USAID, the sector is showing growth due to high level of digitalization of the population, popularity of mobile payments (e.g., monobank), and active support from the National Bank of Ukraine. However, challenges remain - among them: regulatory uncertainty, weak investment attraction, and limited trust in new players.

Domestic researchers (Kholiavko [21]; Popelo, et al. [32]; Shchur et al. [37]) emphasize that Ukraine has significant potential for the FinTech ecosystem, especially in the field of alternative lending, digital wallets and blockchain solutions. A comparison of FinTech ecosystems between EU countries and

Ukraine indicates available common challenges (the need for regulatory adaptation, cybersecurity, data protection) and differences (level of capitalization, access to financing, banks' readiness to innovate) (Shkarlet et al. [40]; Zveryakov et al. [53]). Therefore, studying European experience is extremely valuable for developing effective policies in Ukraine.

A review of available scientific literature provides understanding that FinTech is a powerful driver of transformation of the banking sector in Europe. Ukraine has all prerequisites for repeating a similar trajectory, provided that there is effective policy, support for innovation and attraction of investments, which determines relevance of research on this topic today.

Despite the growing number of scientific studies devoted to the development of FinTech and its impact on banking, the current scientific literature lacks a holistic view of the patterns and models of digital transformation of banking systems in countries with different levels of economic development and financial infrastructure. Most of the works focus on individual aspects of FinTech - technological innovations, regulatory environment or consumer behavior, without providing a comprehensive comparative analysis of structural changes in the banking sector in different national contexts. A separate scientific challenge remains the lack of systematic empirical studies that would integrate the experience of EU countries and Ukraine into a single analytical framework. Ukrainian scientific works mainly focus on the potential of FinTech and individual cases of digital banking services, but do not provide a comparative assessment of the depth and effectiveness of the digital transformation of the banking sector in conditions of institutional instability, regulatory restrictions and military risks. Thus, the research problem lies in the lack of a universal and at the same time adaptive model of FinTech transformation of the banking sector, capable of explaining the unevenness, asymmetry, and multidirectionality of digitalization processes in countries with different levels of development and of forming scientifically based recommendations for regulatory policy, in particular for countries in catching up development, such as Ukraine.

3. METHODOLOGY

To assess the global level of the FinTech implementation in the banking sector, it is recommended to use the IMF Financial Access Survey (FAS) index, which is calculated by the

International Monetary Fund. The FAS structure includes three main categories, namely: access; usage; financial intermediaries and FinTech indicators.

The component related to FinTech in banks covers:

1. Mobile and internet banking transactions.
2. Number of mobile and internet banking transactions.
3. Value of mobile and internet banking transactions.

These indicators reflect the penetration level of FinTech solutions in the banking sector, in particular in terms of digital access, electronic payments and remote banking.

For the analysis, it is recommended to use data from a group of developing European countries (Albania, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Hungary, Kosovo, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Turkey, Ukraine) and compare them with Estonia, a leader in the digital transformation of the state and the banking sector. In addition, Estonia has a similar banking model, structural interaction between banks and FinTech, and is geographically close to the countries of Eastern Europe. The purpose of the study is to analyze the main trends in development of financial technologies in the banking sector of different countries, in particular, to compare digital transformation in developed and developing countries, to identify success factors, development barriers and the potential for integrating innovations into the banking sector. Special attention is paid to determining the role of digital services in transformation of financial infrastructure, as well as assessing prospects for FinTech for countries with a lower level of digitalization, including Ukraine.

4. RESULTS

According to the Financial Stability Board (FSB): Financial Innovation (FinTech) as technologically enabled innovation in financial services that could result in new business models, applications, processes or products with an associated material effect on financial markets and institutions and the provision of financial services. FinTech innovations are affecting many different areas of financial services [13]. Stages of the FinTech development in the banking sector can be divided into three key periods that demonstrate evolution of technology and changing role of banks in the financial system (Fig. 1):

Stage I – FinTech 1.0 (1866 – 1967) – this stage is associated with development of the global financial infrastructure, which laid the foundation

for further digitalization of the banking system. Main characteristics are as follows: emergence of global communication systems: telegraph, telephone, fax; creation of a network of international money transfers; formation of a traditional banking model with a physical presence.

Stage II – FinTech 2.0 (1967 – 2008) – transition to digital banking technologies. This period is associated with penetration of computer technologies into the banking sector: introduction of automated teller machines (ATMs) – the first automation of cash transactions; creation of the SWIFT system for secure exchange of financial messages; active development of electronic banking, bank cards, POS terminals. The key significance of this period is the use of IT solutions by banks to improve efficiency, opening the way to FinTech 3.0 [26].

Stage III – FinTech 3.0 (2008 – present) – innovative transformation and emergence of digital

banks. Characteristic features were as follows: emergence of neobanks (digital-only banks) without physical branches; widespread use of mobile applications, AI, Big Data, cloud technologies, P2P platforms, crowdfunding, cryptocurrency, smart contracts; open banking (Open Banking), API integration. These changes focused on improving personalization, improving the quality of customer service [47].

Digitalization of the financial sector and active integration of financial technologies are significantly transforming the traditional model of bank functioning.

Innovations brought by FinTech have disrupted traditional banking models and opened up new opportunities for financial inclusion, efficiency, and improved customer experience [29; 50; 33].

Figure 1: Evolution of FinTech in the banking sector

Source: Source: summarized by the authors based on Arner et al. [4]

Evolution of FinTech in the banking sector demonstrates gradual transition from physical infrastructure to full digital transformation. A modern bank increasingly resembles a technology company that uses innovation to improve convenience, accessibility, and security of financial services.

Development of mobile banking, open banking, artificial intelligence in scoring, digital customer

identification - all this leads to emergence of a new banking architecture in which FinTech becomes not an external factor, but an integrated part of the banking environment. Fig. 2 depicts transformation of the banking model – from traditional to innovative, functioning in symbiosis with FinTech.

Figure 2: Transformation of the banking model under the influence of FinTech

Source: compiled by the authors

The initial link is the traditional banking model, which is based on physical presence of branches and the use of plastic cards as the main tool for accessing accounts. It is characterized by complex and lengthy lending procedures, as well as the available bulky IT infrastructure, which complicates scaling and adaptation to new technologies.

The next stage of transformation is integration of FinTech technologies, which opens up new opportunities for the banking system. It involves the use of open banking (API) for interaction with financial services, the use of mobile payment solutions (such as Apple Pay and Google Pay).

Digital identification (BankID, Diya.Sign) simplifies access to financial products, and mobile applications and chatbots provide a convenient channel of communication with users.

Due to transformation, the FinTech-integrated banking model is being formed, which involves the operation of digital banks or neobanks without physical branches. This model focuses on providing customers with fast services - instant transfers, microloans, overdrafts - and close cooperation with FinTech companies. It also offers personalized financial products based on the user's behavior analysis, which significantly increases the quality of

service and customer loyalty.

Thus, digitalization is changing the functioning of banks. New competitive challenges are forcing incumbents to rethink their own strengths and vulnerabilities, as well as assess risks and opportunities, which ultimately stimulates changes in their business models [23; 33]. Development of financial technologies is significantly transforming the traditional banking service model, changing both internal operational processes and customer interaction channels. FinTech solutions are gradually being integrated into key areas of the banking activity – from payment services to risk management and investment services. A. Thakor notes that FinTech includes innovations in payment systems (in particular, cryptocurrencies), credit markets (including P2P lending), and in the insurance sector, where blockchain-based smart contracts play an important role [44]. For comprehensive understanding of the scale and effectiveness of this transformation, it is important to systematize FinTech products according to their areas of use and expected benefits for banks. Fig. 3 presents the grouped analysis of FinTech solutions in the banking practice.

Figure 3: FinTech products and areas of banking application

Source: compiled by the authors

The way financial services are provided is changing, there is a need to discuss sustainability, security and competition in the payments sector, foundation is laid for improving transnational money

transfers and the issue of whether private or public money is issued is raised [6]. Application of FinTech products in banking activities and their impact on bank efficiency is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Application of FinTech products in banking activities and their impact on bank efficiency

Scope	FinTech- products / solutions	Bank benefits
Payment Services	- mobile payments (Apple Pay, Google Pay) - QR codes, NFC, P2P - e-wallets (Payoneer, Revolut)	- lower transaction costs - branchless payment infrastructure
Lending	- AI/Big Data scoring - P2P-crediting (Mintos) - BNPL (Buy Now Pay Later)	- rapid decision-making - microloan servicing - new approaches to risk assessment
Deposit Services	- savings applications (e.g. “bank”) - smart deposits with a dynamic rate	- increasing the financial culture of customers - stimulating loyalty through personalized products
Investment Services (WealthTech)	- robo-advisors - trading platforms (securities, bonds) - crowdfunding/crowdfunding	- client access to investment products - reduction in asset management costs
Customer Service	- chatbots (e.g. Gus) - digital identification (BankID, Face ID) - new generation mobile applications	- 24/7 service - less load on contact centers - improved customer interaction
Risk Management and Compliance (RegTech)	- KYC/AML monitoring (automated) - suspicious transaction detection (AI/ML) - cybersecurity	- automation of inspections - fewer human errors - increased trust of regulators
Financial	- BI analytics	- strategic management

Analytics and Reporting	- behavioral analysis of transactions - forecasting of liquidity, profits, risks	- transparency of financial decisions
Banking Infrastructure	- cloud technologies (Cloud banking) - API and Open Banking - Core Banking as a Service	- scalability, flexibility - reduced IT costs - speed of implementation of new services

Source: compiled by the authors

That is, FinTech is a powerful driver of innovation in the banking sector. Their use allows:

- increase operational efficiency through automation and digitalization of processes;
- reduce costs for customer service and infrastructure support;
- expand access to financial services through mobile applications, P2P platforms and cloud solutions;
- improve the customer experience through personalized services, convenience and speed;
- increase reliability and transparency of compliance procedures and risk management.

Generalization shows that implementation of

FinTech solutions is not only a technological trend, but also a strategic necessity to ensure competitiveness of banks in the digital era.

Access to financial services is an important indicator of the digitalization level of banking activities, since it is through digital channels that customers receive fast, convenient and secure access to various banking products and services. To analyze dynamics of the access level to financial services in developing countries in Europe, with a focus on Ukraine and a comparison with Estonia (as a representative of developed digital economies), it is recommended to rely on data from the IMF Financial Access Survey (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Dynamics of access to financial services for developing European countries and Estonia
Source: compiled by the authors based on information from [11]

Between 2016 and 2024, most emerging European countries will see a clear transformation in access to financial services, particularly in the number of ATMs, bank branches and banks in general. The most notable trend is the gradual shift away from physical banking in favour of digital solutions, including FinTech services, which is particularly evident in countries such as Estonia and, to some extent, Ukraine. Estonia is a model of a digital financial model: the number of ATMs per 100,000 population has decreased from 67 in 2016 to 58 in 2023, and the number of branches has almost halved, from 99 to 62. Despite this, access to banking services remains stable thanks to full transition to digital channels, primarily mobile and online banking. It is noteworthy that some banks in Estonia remained stable at 16 throughout the period, indicating a concentrated but efficient system.

In contrast, Ukraine has experienced profound transformation of its banking system, especially after 2020. While in 2016 the country had one of the most extensive networks – over 10 thousand bank branches, 100 banks and 97 ATMs per 100 thousand people – by 2024 these figures had almost halved. The most noticeable decline occurred in 2020-2022. However, it is important to note that against the backdrop of reduction of the physical infrastructure in Ukraine, digital channels – for example, mobile applications, including Monobank and state digital services based on JSC CB “PrivatBank” – have been actively developing.

Poland, Romania, Serbia and Bulgaria show the more gradual reduction in physical presence of banks, which occurs in parallel with introduction of digital services, but without sharp jumps. In these countries, there is gradual decrease in the number of ATMs and branches, as well as slight consolidation of banking institutions, which indicates stable, controlled transformation of the system.

These data allows to identify several patterns. Countries such as Estonia, Poland and, in recent years, Ukraine, demonstrate that active digitalization can compensate for the loss of physical infrastructure. Instead, stable growth of the number of ATMs and bank branches, as in Kosovo and Albania, indicates a stage of the infrastructure development, not its collapse.

Ukraine, in turn, is an exceptional example of forced transformation, where the war became a catalyst for rapid transition to remote banking. Unlike Estonia, which proceeded gradually and deliberately, Ukraine implemented digitalization of banking services at an accelerated pace - largely due to the technical potential, high level of digital literacy and adaptability of citizens.

In general, it can be argued that Europe as a whole, including developing countries, is moving towards reducing physical channels of access to financial services, while stimulating the FinTech development. Estonia is an example of this transition, and Ukraine is an example of a hybrid model.

Developing countries, particularly in Europe, face challenges of modernizing their banking infrastructure, while demonstrating different dynamics of change depending on the digitalization level, macroeconomic conditions and regulatory policies (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Dynamics of mobile and internet banking development for developing European countries and Estonia

Source: compiled by the authors based on information from [11]

The analysis allows to identify dependencies between key indicators of financial infrastructure accessibility and to form assumptions about directions of development of the banking system in the digital economy. Despite the lack of current data on Ukraine in the given sample, it is included in the analysis based on the logic of regional comparison, similarity of structural problems and strategic course on digitalization. This allows to draw general conclusions about possible scenarios for development of the Ukrainian banking infrastructure and to clarify the potential of FinTech solutions as a compensatory mechanism to overcome existing restrictions on access to financial services.

The number of mobile and online banking transactions shows a clear upward trend in all the countries studied – both in the smaller markets of the Western Balkans and in much larger financial systems, including Turkey and Poland. The most notable growth is observed in Turkey, where the volume of transactions increased from 1.08 billion units in 2016 to 11.1 billion units in 2024, i.e. more than tenfold. Poland ranks second in absolute terms. In the Western Balkan countries, the growth dynamics are weaker, but characterized by stability. This indicates gradual expansion of the digital financial sector in conditions of less developed banking infrastructure. Estonia, despite a significant level of digitalization, shows only moderate growth - from 126 to 198 million transactions, which indicates a certain saturation of the market and stable user behavior in the context of already integrated digital services. Particularly dynamic growth was observed in Hungary until 2023, when the volume of transactions increased from 236 million to over 1 billion. However, in 2024, a decrease to 871 million is recorded, which is the result of market correction and structural changes in consumer behavior.

The indicator of the number of transactions per 1,000 adult population gives an idea of the actual penetration level of financial technologies into the daily lives of citizens. The leader among the countries of the region is Estonia, where in 2023 each adult made an average of over 460 mobile or internet banking transactions per year, which indicates almost complete digitalization of the financial sector. High level of activity is also observed in Poland, Turkey and Hungary - with indicators within 90-140 thousand transactions per 1,000 adult population, which indicates available developed digital platforms and widespread use of remote services. In countries, including Serbia, Bulgaria and Romania, an average level of penetration is observed - from 20 to 40 thousand transactions per 1,000 people. Moldova,

Montenegro and North Macedonia demonstrate a gradual increase in this indicator, although they still remain within 25-30 thousand. The lowest values are observed in Albania, Kosovo and Bosnia - up to 7 thousand transactions per 1,000 adults, however, positive dynamics are also recorded in these countries, which indicates the beginning of active development of the FinTech direction.

In regions with a high level of digital transactions, there is also a trend towards a reduction in physical banking infrastructure – a decrease in the number of ATMs and branches, which is well illustrated by examples of Estonia, Poland and Hungary. At the same time, in countries with low level of digitalization, such as Kosovo or Albania, physical service channels remain important for users. Another important indicator is the volume of mobile and online banking transactions as GDP percentage, which demonstrates the depth of integration of digital finance into the country's economy. Poland turned out to be a record holder with an extremely high figure of 2713% of GDP in 2021, although in 2022 it was observed to decrease to 1367% – which is a consequence of both methodological changes and financial shocks. Other countries, in particular Estonia, Hungary and Bulgaria, maintain consistently high values in the range of 400-600%, which indicates overwhelming share of digital channels in the total volume of payments. Turkey, Romania, Serbia and North Macedonia demonstrate average level of this indicator – from 300 to 500% of GDP. In countries with a lower level of FinTech development – Moldova, Montenegro, Kosovo – the volume of digital transactions as a GDP share remains lower, but the growth trend is obvious. In countries such as Albania and Belarus, digital payment systems are at the initial implementation stage, and their share in the economy is still insignificant, but prospects for development remain positive. Although Ukraine is absent from the sample, the analysis suggests that by 2021 it could demonstrate dynamics close to Poland and Hungary, given active spread of mobile banking and development of FinTech services. However, with the outbreak of a full-scale war, digital banking activity has fluctuated, although the demand for remote financial services remained high due to the decrease in available physical infrastructure.

In the comparative analysis of indicators of digital transformation of the banking sector, clear patterns are observed, reflecting the maturity level of FinTech solutions in different countries. The most developed countries in this context are Estonia, Poland and Turkey. They are characterized by a reduction in the number of ATMs and bank

branches, which is accompanied by high volumes of digital transactions per capita and a significant share of these transactions in the GDP structure. This indicates deep integration of FinTech into daily banking operations and complete transition to a fully digital service model. While in these countries digital channels are becoming the main way of interacting with the financial system, less developed markets, in particular Albania, Kosovo, Moldova, demonstrate a different approach. Here there is still gradual expansion of physical banking infrastructure - new branches are opening, the number of ATMs is increasing. At the same time, the growth rate of digital services is also stable, which indicates a trend towards a digital model in the medium term. Although digital indicators in these countries are significantly inferior to leaders, they demonstrate the potential for development.

According to current trends, Ukraine until 2020 was characterized by a significant number of ATMs and extensive physical network of banking institutions. However, with the onset of the pandemic and especially after the start of a full-scale war, digital solutions began to rapidly displace traditional channels. Services such as Privat24, Monobank and others ensured rapid transition of millions of users to remote service. This suggests that today's level of digital banking transactions in Ukraine may be comparable to indicators of countries such as Poland or Hungary. Although the lack of accurate data limits possible direct comparison, structural changes in the country's financial environment indicate a high degree of digital maturity of the banking sector.

5. DISCUSSION

According to Bazilinska et al. [5], Hrubliak et al. [17] and Kovalenko et al. [23], the issue of FinTech and banking sector transformation in European countries remains multidimensional and depends on the level of digital maturity of economies, regulatory environment and readiness of financial institutions for innovations, with which authors fully agree. This is confirmed by the fact that the obtained empirical results allow to interpret the digital transformation of the banking sector as a process of structural restructuring of financial markets, and not only as a technological update of individual services.

Shetakovska et al. [38] and Shkarlet et al. [41] argue that FinTech are changing the logic of banking, shifting the focus from physical presence and product-based approaches to customer-centric digital ecosystems. Studies [7; 18; 19] show that this transformation enhances the role of data, transaction processing speed, and personalization of financial

services as key factors of competitiveness.

Shkolnyk et al. [43], Tkachuk [45] argue that alternative financial technologies, such as open banking, digital payments, neobanks and artificial intelligence-based platforms, contribute to increasing the competitiveness of the financial sector and fill gaps that traditional banks are not always able to effectively cover. In this context, the study shows that European countries demonstrate different models of interaction between banks and FinTech companies - from cooperative approaches to competitive confrontation.

An important analytical result is the identification of an asymmetry between the speed of technological implementation and the adaptation of the regulatory environment. In a number of countries, digital financial services are developing faster than the regulatory framework, which creates both opportunities for innovation and additional risks for financial stability and consumer protection [28; 48; 52]. This confirms the need to move from reactive to proactive regulation of fintech [31; 46; 49].

Thus, the transformation of the banking sector can occur either through the integration of fintech innovations into traditional financial institutions or through the development of independent digital financial ecosystems. This difference in strategic approaches not only reflects national economic and social characteristics, but also forms the prerequisites for structural changes in the European financial sector in the medium term.

For Ukraine, the potential for FinTech development is significant, given the high level of digitalization of payment services and the active implementation of state digital platforms. At the same time, further transformation of the banking sector requires improving the regulatory framework, harmonization with European standards and stimulating the innovation environment. The experience of European countries can serve as a guideline for the formation of a balanced development model that combines financial stability with technological progress. Thus, the extended analysis confirms that effective digital transformation of the banking sector requires a systemic approach that covers technological, regulatory and behavioral aspects.

Therefore, this study complements scientific developments in the field of financial technologies and banking transformation, summarizing European experience and identifying prospects for its adaptation to Ukrainian conditions, taking into account current economic and institutional challenges.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The main trends in the FinTech development in the banking sector include deep digital transformation of financial services, focused on convenience, accessibility and efficiency of customer service. Globally, there is consistent transition from traditional physical banking infrastructure (branches, ATMs) to digital channels, in particular mobile and Internet banking. In countries with developed financial systems (such as Estonia, Poland, Turkey), this process is accompanied by a decrease in the number of banking institutions and active implementation of innovative services - digital wallets, instant payments, Open Banking, e-KYC, biometric identification, etc.

The study showed the unevenness and asymmetry of the digital transformation of the banking sector under the influence of FinTech between countries with different levels of economic development and financial infrastructure.

In some European countries (Estonia, Poland, Turkey), FinTech is actually replacing traditional physical banking channels, which is manifested in the reduction of the network of branches and ATMs while simultaneously sharply increasing the number and value of digital transactions. In other countries (Albania, Kosovo, Moldova, Bosnia and Herzegovina), FinTech has not yet become a full-fledged alternative to traditional banking infrastructure, and digital services are developing in parallel with the physical expansion of the network. Ukraine is characterized by forced and uneven digitalization, when a sharp reduction in physical banking infrastructure is combined with the rapid growth of remote financial services, but official statistics do not always allow to fully assess the scale of these changes.

Thus, the study showed that FinTech does not form a single universal trajectory of development of banking systems, but is implemented through different models, determined by institutional conditions, the level of digital maturity of the population and the features of the regulatory environment. This necessitates a comparative analysis and search for adaptive models of digital banking, taking into account national characteristics.

The scientific contribution of the study is to systematize approaches to assessing the impact of FinTech on the banking sector through a combination of indicators of digital activity and physical banking infrastructure, as well as to identify typical transformation models for different groups of countries. The results obtained can be used as an analytical basis for the formation of state policy and regulatory strategies in the field of digital banking,

especially for countries that are at the stage of catching up.

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REFERENCES:

- [1] Abramova, A., Popelo, O., Fedyshyn, M., Popova, L., Shchur, R., & Marych, M. (2024). Digital Green Finance Architecture in the Context of Green Deal Implementation: Modern Fintech Tools and Solutions Under the Sustainable Development Concept. *Journal of Lifestyle and SDGs Review*, 4(2), e02166. <https://doi.org/10.47172/2965-730X.SDGsReview.v4.n02.pe02166>

- [2] Aldarmi, A.A. (2024). Fintech Service Quality of Saudi Banks: Digital Transformation and Awareness in Satisfaction, Re-Use Intentions, and the Sustainable Performance of Firms. *Sustainability*, 16(6), 2261. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16062261>
- [3] Aliexsieiev, I., Zhelizniak, R., Glielova, N., Pavlenko, L., Kovalenko, V., & Zhytar, M. (2023). Development of the Model for Forecasting Indicators of Banking Microcrediting of Small Business Entities. *Financial and Credit Activity Problems of Theory and Practice*, 2(49), pp. 163–180. <https://doi.org/10.55643/fcaptop.2.49.2023.4025>
- [4] Arner, D.W., Barberis, J.N., Buckley, R.P. (2015). The evolution of fintech: a new post-crisis paradigm? *University of Hong Kong Faculty of Law Research Paper*, 2015/047, 2016-62. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2676553>
- [5] Bazilinska, O., Dubyna, M., Panchenko, O., Sadchykova, I., Kozlianchenko, A., & Tarasenko, A. (2023). The Role and Prospects of the Use of Artificial Intelligence Technology in the Credit Activities OF Banking Institutions. *Review of Economics and Finance*, 21, pp. 2042-2051. <https://refpress.org/ref-vol21-a220>
- [6] Broby, D. (2021). Financial technology and the future of banking. *Financial Innovation*, 7(47). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-021-00264-y>
- [7] Buiak, L., Hryhorkiv, M., Hryhorkiv, V., Bashutska, O., & Pryshliak, K. (2023). Computer Modeling of the Economy Dynamics of Ukraine, Taking into Account the Socio-Economic Clustering of Society. *Journal of Information Technology Management*, 15(4), pp. 64-79. <https://doi.org/10.22059/jitm.2023.94710>
- [8] Bukhtiarova, A.G., Shkolnik I.O., & Semenog, A.U. (2017). Economic Modeling of Assessment of Ukrainian Banking System. *Financial and Credit Activity Problems of Theory and Practice*, 2(23), pp. 337–344. <https://doi.org/10.18371/fcaptop.v2i23.121901>
- [9] Dubyna, M., Popelo, O., Zhavoronok, A., Lopashchuk, I., & Fedyshyn, M. (2023). Development of the credit market of Ukraine under macroeconomic instability. *Public and Municipal Finance*, 12(1), pp. 33-47. [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/pmf.12\(1\).2023.04](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/pmf.12(1).2023.04)
- [10] European Central Bank (1999). The Effects of Technology on the EU Banking Systems. European Central Bank. <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/other/techbnken.pdf>
- [11] Financial Access Survey (FAS). International Monetary Fund (2025). Available at: <https://data.imf.org/en/datasets/IMF.STA:FAS>
- [12] Financial Stability Board (2020). Available at: <https://www.fsb.org/work-of-the-fsb/financial-innovation-and-structural-change/fintech>
- [13] FinTech, Supervisory and Regulatory Issues that Merit Authorities' Attention (2017). The FSB has analysed the benefits and risks related to financial technology innovations from a financial stability perspective, and provides a definition in page 7 of its report Financial Stability Implications.
- [14] Gancarczyk, M., Łasak, P., & Gancarczyk, J. (2022). The fintech transformation of banking: Governance dynamics and socio-economic outcomes in spatial contexts. *Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review*, 10(3), pp. 143-165. <https://doi.org/10.15678/EBER.2022.100309>
- [15] Hidayat-ur-Rehman, I., Hossain, MdN. (2024). The impacts of Fintech adoption, green finance and competitiveness on banks' sustainable performance: digital transformation as moderator. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJBA-10-2023-0497>
- [16] Hrubliak, O., Popelo, O., Shaposhnykov, K., Zhavoronok, A., Ostrovska, N., Krylov, D. (2024). Digital Currency of the Central Banks: Trends of the Euro Area and Prospects of the Use Within the Implementation of the European Green Deal. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 102(7), pp. 2954-2967. <https://www.jatit.org/volumes/Vol102No7/17Vol102No7.pdf>
- [17] Hrubliak, O., Zhavoronok, A., Popelo, O., Kharabara, V., Dubyna, M., & Lopashchuk, I. (2025). The impact of financial globalization on the economic growth of countries: A case for Ukraine. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 22(4), pp. 209-226. [https://doi.org/10.21511/imfi.22\(4\).2025.17](https://doi.org/10.21511/imfi.22(4).2025.17)
- [18] Hryhorkiv, V., Buiak, L., Verstiak, A., Hryhorkiv, M., Verstiak, O., & Berdnuk, A. (2019). Mining credit interest rate data from multiple data sources. *9th International Conference on Advanced Computer Information Technologies* (pp. 265-268). Ceske Budejovice, Czech Republic.

- <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACITT.2019.8780034>
- [19] Hryhoruk, I., Yakubiv, V., Sydoryk, Y., Maksymiv, Y., & Popadynets, N. (2021). Modelling of Prognosis for Bioenergy Production in Ukraine. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 11(6), pp. 27–34. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijeep.11741>
- [20] Ivashchenko, A., Britchenko, I., Dyba, M., Polishchuk, Ye., Sybirianska, Yu., & Vasylyshen, Yu. (2018). Fintech platforms in SME's financing: EU experience and ways of their application in Ukraine. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 15(3), pp. 83-96. [https://dx.doi.org/10.21511/imfi.15\(3\).2018.07](https://dx.doi.org/10.21511/imfi.15(3).2018.07)
- [21] Kholiavko, N., Dubyna, M., Zhavoronok, A., Safonov, Yu., Krylov, D., Tochylina, Yu. (2022). The ICT sector in economic development of the countries of Eastern Europe: a comparative analysis. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 19, pp. 169-185. <https://doi.org/10.37394/23207.2022.19.18>
- [22] Khudolei, V., Dubyna, M., Karpenko, O., Rohova, O., Zaiets, O., & Ustinov, Y. (2024). Ensuring Cybersecurity in Action Electronic Commerce Enterprises in the Conditions of Implementation of the Sustainable Development Model. *Journal of Lifestyle and SDGs Review*, 4(2), e02463. <https://doi.org/10.47172/2965-730X.SDGsReview.v4.n02.pe02463>
- [23] Kovalenko, V., Kuznetsova, L., Sergeeva, E., Todorova, N., Mylashko, O., & Tej, J. (2019). Cluster approach to banking supervision with reference to bank risk profile. *Economic Annals-XXI*, 177(5-6), pp. 82-91. <https://doi.org/10.21003/ea.V177-07>
- [24] Kozmenko, S., Shkolnyk, I., Kozmenko, O., Orlov, V., & Shukairi, F. (2021). Modeling of the financial systems stability on the example of Ukraine. Equilibrium. *Quarterly Journal of Economics and Economic Policy*, 16(2), pp. 377-411. <https://doi.org/10.24136/eq.2021.014>
- [25] Kychko, I., Shaposhnykova, I., Popelo, O., Shaposhnykov, K., Tochylina, Y., Stoika, V. (2023). The Role of Digital Technologies in Balancing the Labor Market in the Conditions of the Post-War Recovery of the Ukraine's Economy. *Review of Economics and Finance*, 21, pp. 1991-2002. <https://doi.org/10.55365/1923.x2023.21.214>
- [26] Łasak, P. and Williams, J. (2023). Digital Transformation and the Economics of Banking. *1st edn. Routledge*. London: W. W. Norton & Company.
- [27] Li, X. (2023). Impact of fintech on bank risks: the role of bank digital transformation. *Applied Economics Letters*, 32(6), pp. 895–899. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2023.2291085>
- [28] Maksymiv, Y., Yakubiv, V., Pylypiv, N., Piatnychuk, I., Hryhoruk, I., & Hokh, V. (2022). Biological assets in accounting of socially responsible activities of agricultural enterprises *Custos e Agronegocio*, 18(2), pp. 458-476.
- [29] Mărăcine, V., Voican, O. & Scarlat, E. (2020). The Digital Transformation and Disruption in Business Models of the Banks under the Impact of FinTech and BigTech. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Excellence*, 14(1), 2020. pp. 294-305. <https://doi.org/10.2478/picbe-2020-0028>
- [30] Melnyk, V., Zhytar, M., Shchur, R., Kriuchkova, N., & Solodzhuk, T. (2021). Assessment of the performance of the financial architecture of the Ukrainian economy: Budgetary, stock and social aspects. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 18, pp. 386-395. <https://doi.org/10.37394/23207.2021.18.39>
- [31] Pilko, A., Shchur, R., Chepyha, B., Sakun, O., & Matskiv, V. (2024). Analysis of the Influence of Monetary Instruments on the Size of the Domestic Public Debt. *Financial and Credit Activity Problems of Theory and Practice*, 5(58), pp. 49-60. <https://doi.org/10.55643/fcapt.5.58.2024.4499>
- [32] Popelo, O., Tulchynska, S., Andriushchenko, O., Shepelenko, S., Falko, M., Shut, S. (2024). Blockchain technologies as a factor of the financial sustainability management of the enterprise and the e-commerce development. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 102(17), pp. 6302-6316. <https://www.jatit.org/volumes/Vol102No17/1Vol102No17.pdf>
- [33] Sajid, R., Ayub, H., Malik, B.F., Ellahi, A. (2023). The Role of Fintech on Bank Risk-Taking: Mediating Role of Bank's Operating Efficiency. *Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies*, pp. 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/7059307>

- [34] Savchenko, T., Koibichuk, V., Boyko, A., & Minchenko, M. (2020). Risk Assessment of the Banking Groups Usage in the Shadow Activities. *Financial and Credit Activity Problems of Theory and Practice*, 4(35), pp. 37–43. <https://doi.org/10.18371/fcaptp.v4i35.221737>
- [35] Serdarušić, H., Pancić, M., & Zavišić, Ž. (2024). Green Finance and Fintech Adoption Services among Croatian Online Users: How Digital Transformation and Digital Awareness Increase Banking Sustainability. *Economies*, 12(3), pp. 54. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies12030054>
- [36] Shaposhnykov, K., Kochubei, O., Grygor, O., Protsenko, N., Vyshnevska, O., Dzyubina, A. (2021). Organizational and Economic Mechanism of Development and Promotion of IT Products in Ukraine. *Estudios de economía aplicada*, 39(6). <https://doi.org/10.25115/eea.v39i6.5264>
- [37] Shchur, R., Pilko, A., Chepyha, B., Bilyi, M., & Stabias, S. (2025). Application of Sem and Qardl Models in the Practice of Analysis of the Influence of Exchange Rate Volatility on Macroeconomic Indicators Financial and Credit Activity Problems of Theory and Practice, 1(60), pp. 20–32. <https://doi.org/10.55643/fcaptp.1.60.2025.4669>
- [38] Shestakovska, T., Briushkova, N., Semchenko-Kovalchuk, O., Marchenko, N., Zholobetska, M., & Nikolayenko, Y. (2024). Finance as a critical component of successful implementation of creative innovations in the modern economic system. *Multidisciplinary Science Journal*, 6, 2024ss0222. <https://doi.org/10.31893/multiscience.2024ss0222>
- [39] Shkarlet, S., & Dubyna, M. (2016). Features of the cognitive approach application to the essence of the financial services market identification. *Economic Annals-XXI*, 158(3-4(2)), pp. 70-74. <https://doi.org/10.21003/ea.V158-16>
- [40] Shkarlet, S., Dubyna, M., Shchur, R., & Shyshkina, O. (2025). The Role of Cloud Technologies in Modern Development of Banking Institutions. *Journal of Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University*, 12(2), pp. 143-157. <https://doi.org/10.15330/jpnu.12.2.143-157>
- [41] Shkarlet, S., Dubyna, M., Vovk, V., & Noga, M. (2019). Financial service markets of Eastern Europe: a compositional model. *Economic Annals-XXI*, 176(3-4), pp. 26-37. <https://doi.org/10.21003/ea.V176-03>
- [42] Shkolnyk, I. O. (2008). Peculiarities of financial markets functioning in developing countries in the context of financial globalization. *Actual Problems of Economics*, 84, pp. 63-66.
- [43] Shkolnyk, I., Kozmenko, S., Kozmenko, O., & Mershchii, B. (2019). The Impact of the Economy Financialization on the Level of Economic Development of the Associate EU Member States. *Economics & Sociology*, 12(4), pp. 43-58. <https://doi.org/10.14254/2071-789X.2019/12-4/2>
- [44] Thakor, A.V. (2020). Fintech and banking: What do we know? *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 41, 100833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfi.2019.100833>
- [45] Tkachuk, I. (2017). Asset operations of Ukrainian banks on the current stage of banking system development. *Banks and Bank Systems*, 12(1-1), pp. 119-127. [https://doi.org/10.21511/bbs.12\(1-1\).2017.04](https://doi.org/10.21511/bbs.12(1-1).2017.04)
- [46] Tulchynska, S., Pohrebniak, A., Zybarena, O., Pozhydaieva, M., Solosich, O., & Vakulenko, A. (2024). Analysis of the Security Development of Business Entities in the Conditions of Artificial Intellectualization of the Global Space. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 102(21), pp. 7876-7886. <https://www.jatit.org/volumes/Vol102No21/24Vol102No21.pdf>
- [47] Van De Venn, P. (2023). *Digital Banking trends.VP Business Development Digital & Software EMEA: Building digital solutions that provide real value*. Available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/digital-banking-trends-peter-jan-van-de-venn>
- [48] Verstiak, A., Hryhorkiv, V., Buiak, L., Hryhorkiv, M., O. & Verstiak, O. (2021). Ecological Footprint Impact Factors Forecasts using VAR Model: Decision Making Case Study From Ukraine. *Proceedings International Conference on Advanced Computer Information Technologies Acit*, pp. 19-22. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACIT52158.2021.9548526>
- [49] Vovk, V., Denysova, A., Rudoi, K., & Kyrychenko, T. (2021). Management and legal aspects of the symbiosis of banking institutions and fintech companies in the credit services

- market in the context of digitization. *Estudios de Economía Aplicada*, 39(7).
<https://doi.org/10.25115/eea.v39i7.5013>
- [50] Yin, M. (2022). *Fintech opportunities for commercial banks under the COVID-19*. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.23977/msied2022.010>
- [51] Zagirniak, D., Shalimova, N., Akmalidnova, O., Stezhko, Y., Perevozniuk, V. (2023). Transformation of Education in the Context of Modern Informational and Cultural Realities of Artificial Intelligence ChatGPT Application. *2023 IEEE 5th International Conference on Modern Electrical and Energy System (MEES)*, pp. 1-6.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/MEES61502.2023.10402376>
- [52] Zhavoronok, A., Shchur, R., Zhezherun, Y., Sadchykova, I., Viadrova, N., & Tychkovska, L. (2022). The role of the credit services market in ensuring the stability of the banking system. *International Journal of Safety and Security Engineering*, 12(6), pp. 667-679.
<https://doi.org/10.18280/ijssse.120602>
- [53] Zveryakov, M., Kovalenko, V., Sheludko, S., & Sharah, E. (2019). FinTech sector and banking business: competition or symbiosis? *Economic Annals-XXI*, 175(1-2), pp. 53-57.
<https://doi.org/10.21003/ea.V175-09>
- [54] Zybareva, O., Kravchuk, I., Pushak, Y., Verbivska, L., Makeieva, O. (2021). Economic and Legal Aspects of the Network Readiness of the Enterprises in Ukraine in the Context of Business Improving. *Estudios de economía aplicada*, 39(5).
<https://doi.org/10.25115/eea.v39i5.4972>